

SOCIO-CULTURAL STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ARÁMOKỌ LAND: A HISTORICAL REFLECTION

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Abstract:

This paper examined the socio-cultural composition and development in pre-colonial Arámokọ-land. It describes and analyzes the various social stages recorded during the pre-colonial era as well as the human adaptive measure put in place for the various established structures. It further opined that the community; Arámokọ, possess in large extent, the various social and cultural formations as well as a good climate to sustain its inhabitants and future generations from going into extinction. The value of marriage, family as well as other social and cultural habits i.e. hairdo, arts and craft are considered in the paper. The paper however derives its data from both primary and secondary sources.

Keywords: socio-cultural, Arámokọ, pre-colonial, development

1. Introduction

It is important to acknowledge the historical documentations of Samuel Johnson and J. A. Atanda whose different accounts has been of enormous assistant in the oral analyses of the various settlements that made up present day Yoruba land. A few works however has Phn done by local historians with direct or indirect reference to the works of Johnson and Atanda on the examination of Arámokọ history. S. O. Johnson classified the Èkìtìs' as among the aboriginal elements of the country absorbed by the invaders from the East.ⁱⁱ He further opined that the Èkìtì country is divided into 16 districts with its own kings. He grouped only four of these kings as supreme ruler with more and

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ⁱⁱ S. O. Johnson. *The History of the Yorubas*, London: Lowe and Brydone Printers Limited, 1921. P. 22

significant link to the progenitor of Yoruba land; Oduduwa. Although the Alára of Arámokọ didn't fall within the supreme rulers of Èkìtì land, but scholars are of the view that the folklore links between him and Ajero and Orangun Ile Ula point to the fact that he has a very special relationship with the family of Oduduwa during the migration epoch.ⁱⁱⁱ The focus of this paper is not the historical origin of the Arámokọ people, but rather their socio-cultural institutions and activities prior to the coming of the Europeans.

1.1 Settlement Pattern in Brief Discuss

Arámokọ has been a part of the Èkìtì land;^{iv} managed and controlled by its own traditional ruler (Alára) and his council of chiefs (Alára in council). Each region has its own head called 'baálè' or 'Olóyè' while the kingdom itself is been represent by the 'Alára'.^v The chiefs are exceptional counsels to the ruler who likewise had minor chiefs responsible for different exercises in their different sub-regions. Prior to the coming of western civilization, houses in Arámokọ were made of mud dividers and palm leaves or different leaves for roofing. About every one of the structures had a similar outline and size; which are all controlled by the utilitarian and residential needs of the general population.

Each compound has its own 'Agba-Ile'- normally the oldest male in the family who fill in as the overseer of their standards and norms. They play out the part of peace-making or mediators in time of intra or inter families' misunderstanding before it gets to the traditional ruler; if need be. Young ladies in each compound are saddled with the duty of sweeping the compound while the young men do the clearing of brambles or homesteads for agrarian purposes. Waterways or streams in Arámokọ are called "Aretí"^{vi} usually named after the major 'Olóyè'^{vii} of the area where the river or stream is located, and they had never dried up since their creation.

The climate in Arámokọ follows the tropic pattern;^{viii} which consisted of two separate seasons. The first season is the rainy season, usually between the month of April and the month of October of every year, while the dry season is usually between the month November and month of March. Rainfall varies in its increase and decrease.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ibid p. 65 See also J. A. Atanda. *An introduction to Yoruba History*, Ibadan, University Press, 1980

^{iv} S. O. Johnson. *The History of the Yorubas*, London: Lowe and Brydone Printers Limited, 1921. P. 26

^v Districts like Alafe, Ile ona, Ajaye, Orisumibare, Ajebamidele, Oke Akola, Oko Ogboni, Oko Sajowa, and Oke Obo all have their own Baale as the district head and answer directly to the Alara. Interview with Chief S. O. Osadola, a traditional chief of Arámokọ on the 15th December 2017, see also R. S. Smith, *Kingdoms of the Yoruba*, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press, 1988.

^{vi} "Areti in Arámokọ are local streams in which has a direct link to major rivers in Yoruba land including river Osun. These local stream includes Urara, Ejigbo, Abami, Abamiyo, and Okeoja," Interview with Chief S. O. Osadola, a traditional chief of Arámokọ on the 15th December 2017, see also S. O. Biobaku, *Sources of Yoruba History*, New York: Clarendon Press, 1973

^{vii} Areti Abami was named after the family of the late Chief Amos Ojo Osadola not only for his role in the development of the town but for the fact that the stream actually flow through the back door of his family house. Interview with Chief Ogunleye, a traditional chief of Arámokọ on the 23rd January 2018 C See also R. S. Smith, *Kingdoms of the Yoruba*, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press, 1988.

^{viii} A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 21

The winds are the south-west moisture carrying-wind that brings rainfall while also the North-east trade winds that brings dryness/harmattan. The temperature ranges from 85° F to 65° F.^{ix} The relative humidity is very high. There is luxuriant growth in the vegetating tropical evergreen forest and tropical grassland are also found in the area.

Between January and July, the average temperature falls between 70°F and 80°F respectively and it is conducive for human habitation.^x The favourable climate conditions also favours the planting and other agricultural product such as timber, cocoyam, vegetables, okro, and the likes; which are used in feeding the population of the community.

2. Socio-cultural Activities among the Arámokọ people – A Discourse

Social institutions in pre-colonial Arámokọ Èkìtì constituted the following:

A. Family

The all-inclusive community of Arámokọ Èkìtì has a family structure, which is outstandingly exceptional. It is one of a kind simple because it is network based and a unique type of grass root government. It is upon this grass root government that different levels of government inside the general public are constructed.^{xi} There are two level of family division among the general population of Arámokọ Èkìtì to be specific; immediate or nuclear family level and the extended family level. These two levels feature both blood and conjugal connections. In any case, usually, the most essential and exceedingly featured family connections are along blood lines. Arámokọ families are generally patrilineal and patrilocal in nature.^{xii}

The nuclear family comprises of the father (Baba), mother (Mama/Iya) and the kids (Omo). Polygamy is allowed among the Arámokọ Èkìtì; men can marry as many wives as possible. The spouses and the stepbrothers/sisters (Obakan) in a polygamous family still constitute parts of the nuclear family. It is the obligation of the father to care and fend for the whole family and particularly the children. He accommodates every one of their needs. The customary Aramoko society is agrarian in nature; the kids figure out how to cultivate until the point that they are develop enough to have their own particular separate bit of land. In the option, the dad may search for proper exchange or livelihood for them. The young men got their freedom when they are hitched and begin their own autonomous lives yet inside a similar compound. The young ladies, then again were hitched out into different families. The mother fills in as the principle 'task director' inside the nuclear family. She turned into a spouse, a mother and the director

^{ix} Ibid

^x A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 54

^{xi} E. A. Kenyo, E. A., *Origin of the Progenitor of the Yoruba Race*, Lagos: Yoruba Historical Research Co. 1951

^{xii} Interview with Chief Ogunleye, 56, a traditional chief of Arámokọ Èkìtì, 27/01/2018, he explained further that the family divisions are usually recognized along the male bloodlines

of the family unit economy.^{xiii} She adds to the ranch work, carters to the need of the family and she is for the most part in charge of sustaining and specifically forming the character of the children, particularly the young ladies. When the parent grows old, children are relied upon to take supreme care of them by accommodating every one of their needs. "Bi okete ba dagba, omu omo re n ii mu", signifying, 'when the hedge rodent progressed in age, it relies upon its child's breast milk for survival.'^{xiv}

The extended family framework is another layer of structure higher than the nuclear family. It comprises of a gathering of families who follow their inception to a typical predecessor. Individuals from the more distant family normally live in a huge exacerbate (a round structure with a patio at the inside). It comprises of the greatest number of nuclear families as they can have inside the compound. They carry on with a network based life. The agboole or agbo ile (family compound) is headed by the Baale-ile (Head of the family). He is the agent of the whole extended family in the town or town committee. He goes about as the overseer of the family properties and furthermore guarantees that the graveyard (oju-oori) of his ancestors is well cared for. He ensures that the family gods are revered as at when due. He guarantees that there is peace and peacefulness inside the ebi or family by settling all scores and question that may emerge. He is the caretaker of (the) family custom and learning. He may not really be the most extravagant among the men inside the extended family; however, he is the most established. At whatever point he kicks the bucket, the title isn't given to his child (Àrèmo), however, it is given to the oldest living male inside the family.^{xv}

The Ba-álé is likewise assisted by the Ìyálé who is the general leader of the women inside the extended family. She is typically the most seasoned among the women fold. She appropriates and allocates obligations to other ladies inside the family. She likewise settles question among ladies. At whatever point there are capacities or function inside the agbo-ilé, she co-ordinates the cooking and serving of sustenance. She helps the Ba-álé in the everyday running of the agbo-ilé. Much of the time, when other ladies go out each day to buy and sell; they all leave their kids with her and she goes about as the caretaker for the agbo-ilé.^{xvi}

The whole individuals inside the compound carry on with a public life. Somebody's business is everyone's business. At whatever point anyone has anything to do or he's influenced by anything, the whole family (ẹbí) rally round him or her. As

^{xiii} S. O. Johnson. *The History of the Yorubas*, London: Lowe and Brydone Printers Limited, 1921. P. 22, see also S. A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 21, O Soetan, *Èkìtì: Studies in Èkìtì History (Part I)*. Ilorin: Majab Publishers, 2006

^{xiv} Interview with Madam Fabian Ojo Fasakin, 86 years, trader from Arámokò Èkìtì, 21st March 2018. She emphasized the benefits of child bearing as a vital necessity that helps grow the population as well as the blood lines amongst the people of Aramoko Ekiti

^{xv} Interview with Chief Ogunleye, 56, a traditional chief of Arámokò Èkìtì, 27/01/2018 see also A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 21, O Soetan, *Èkìtì: Studies in Èkìtì History (Part I)*. Ilorin: Majab Publishers, 2006

^{xvi} Ibid

event requests, the whole extended family wears a similar kind of dress, or attires (asq-èbí) whenever one of them is celebrating any occasion.^{xvii}

Older members of the family treat the young ones equally without segregation. The younger ones however give necessary respect to their elders no matter what. The whole families are bound together by family ties (alájòbí) and no one sets out to conflict with the standards and estimations of the family. Anyone that does this, the soul of their progenitors (Òkú-Òrun) is summoned and the outcomes might be catastrophic for such person.^{xviii} The Arámokọ Èkìtì also treasured family levels to a very large extent.

They trust that anybody with whom they have blood relations inside the extended family is often of a similar dad and mother. They had only five words with which they indicate family connections. These are: Bàbá (Father); Ìyá/Màmá (Mother); Ègbón (Older in age); Àbúrò (Younger in age); and Ọmo (Child).

There was not much indistinctness about these above kinship terms and their usage. Any man within the extended family who was probably old enough to be one's father is regarded as father (Bàbá); likewise, any woman who is old enough to be one's mother is regarded as mother (Ìyá/Màmá). Any man or woman who is older than someone but not enough to be one's father or mother is regarded as senior (Ègbón). Likewise, anyone within the family that is younger to someone is regarded junior (Àbúrò).^{xix} All within the family that were likely to be old or less than one's son or daughter are regarded as child (Ọmo): Arámokọ Èkìtì culture abhors the use of the following phrases: My father's younger brother; My father's elder brother; My mother's younger sister; and My mother's elder sister.

Whenever they are used, they are interpreted to mean that the speaker is overtly expressing the wish to distance himself/herself from the addressees. It is a subtle of any intimate relationship. The implication of the usage is that it invariably causes a breakdown of harmonious relationship within the family.^{xx} Instead of the previous phrases, they use the following phrases in replacement: Bàbá kékeré (younger or small father); Bàbá àgbà (older or big father); Ìyá /màmá kékeré (younger or small mother); Ìyá /màmá àgbà (older or big mother).

These terms, along with references to vocation, residence (if the person in question resides outside the compound) and so on, can also be used to identify the many different bàbá (father) and ìyá (mother) that a person has within the extended family.^{xxi}

Family occupies a pre-eminent place in the live of Arámokọ people, regardless; every Arámokọ Èkìtì child is born into a home, which is a part of a compound or a clan. Family members always trace their descent to a common ancestor, inheritance is

^{xvii} A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 63

^{xviii} Interview with Chief S. O. Osadola, a traditional chief of Arámokọ on the 15th December 2017

^{xix} Interview with Chief S. O. Osadola, a traditional chief of Arámokọ on the 15th December 2017 see also A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 63

^{xx} See also J. A. Atanda. *An introduction to Yoruba History*, Ibadan, University Press, 1980 and S. O. Biobaku, *Sources of Yoruba History*, New York: Clarendon Press, 1973

^{xxi} Interview with Mr. Ayeni, retired civil servant from Arámokọ Èkìtì, 67, 21st March, 2018 see also A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 63

matrilineal. Culturally, male children are favoured, because of the biological and subsequent social role in the community; while female children are accorded limited relevancies and most times do not receive inheritance from their birth-homes.

In any Arámokọ Èkìtì homes (monogamy/polygamy), family is made up of father, wife or wives as the case may be in a polygamous home and the children; moreover, the extended family members from both the father and the mother sides.^{xxii} The traditional roles of the father then and now have not changed, rather, have increased. In times past, fathers were to provide shelter, food, pre-occupied with the general well-being of the entire family members, he consulted oracles (Ifa) in times of trouble, and lead other family members in every religious and ceremonies that had direct bearings on his family. Fathers or adult males, even as of today hold and keep collective families property such as (farmlands, act as custodian of families traditional and religious birthright titles). In modern times, fathers performed these functions, even do more. They send their kids to school from elementary to high school: those that are wealthy enough send their children to colleges and universities.^{xxiii}

Besides, fathers render other socially/legally placed responsibilities over known or not common in the ancient times. Fathers represent and take decisions on behalf of families on community matters. In the ancient times, wives/mothers were always at home to take care of the children, supporting husbands in whatever ways possible. They served as advisers, counselors to husbands, represented husbands in absence, served as moral guardians to their children. The older wives in homes trained the new ones, in some cases, served as custodians of family values and traditions.^{xxiv} Even as of today with western education, industrialization, Christianity and Islam which to a reasonable extent have changed and re-defined woman's status in today's world, still, they performed these traditional functions as home-makers, in conjunction with their secular jobs or new roles. Being an agnatic and communal-oriented society, family members live side-by-side, or near ancestral homes for continuity of the extended family. The most senior/oldest male in the entire compound becomes family head (Mògàjí Olóri-Ebí), the position goes to another most senior, when the holder dies or becomes incapacitated because of infirmity, due to old age and illness.^{xxv}

Traditional Arámokọ Èkìtì homes before the arrival of the Europeans were rectangular-shaped-multi-single-rooms, with corridors and central compound and open space at the back, where children played at night. The affluent Yoruba may have several of these homes to provide shelter needs for: wives, several children, family dependents and slaves.^{xxvi}

Those who had domestic animals like: goats, sheep, cattle, pigs (fowl of different kinds), had low-built-pen-house. Family head lived in the same house, but in a separate

^{xxii} S. O. Biobaku, *Sources of Yoruba History*, New York: Clarendon Press, 1973 see also J. F. Oloidi, *The Economic History of Èkìtì*, PhD Thesis, University of Nsukka, 2011

^{xxiii} S. O Johnson. *The History of the Yorubas*, London: Lowe and Brydone Printers Limited, 1921.

^{xxiv} Interview with Mr. Ogundele, 70years old, retired civil servant from Arámokọ, 21st March, 2018

^{xxv} Interview with Mr. Ogundele, 70years old, retired civil servant from Arámokọ, 21st March, 2018 see also R. S. Smith, *Kingdoms of the Yoruba*, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press, 1988

^{xxvi} R. S. Smith, *Kingdoms of the Yoruba*, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press, 1988

room. In a polygamous home, each wife had personal room, which she shared with her under-aged; adult males shared same room, while females lived in the same room. Each wife took turn to sleep with their husband, even in one-man-one wife home, couples lived under this arrangement.

B. Marriage

Marriage is one of the oldest institutions among the Arámokọ people, it marks the beginning of a new era between two different individuals, who agreed to live together and their union creates everlasting friendship between homes of their birth.^{xxvii}

In time past, marriage matter were not left in the hands of the prospective couples, rather, they were families' affairs. Several steps were required before marriage could be consummated,^{xxviii} though, things have really changed; yet some of these step are still valid and observed in marriage journey of modern day couples, because of their cultural relevance.

These various steps in marriage include; Searching for spouse which is usually initiated by males (Òfojúsóde), Wall-scratching time (Ìdégìrì), Acceptance (Ìsíùn), Family soliciting (Ìtoro), Betrothal (Ìdána), and lastly, Marriage proper/bride hand-over (Ìgbéyàwó)^{xxix}

Searching for a spouse begins with a man, when he is of age. The potential groom begins visiting community's night market, local streams (where laundry is done, mostly by maiden), public square, and other female centers.^{xxx}

Another search method is either through friends who have female siblings, or through married couples who had interest in giving out their relatives whom might be single.^{xxxi}

At times, parents do the search, by looking out for a well-behaved child from a reputable home; sometimes, parents arrange for a union between their wards in order to create lasting friendship.

Regardless of the search method, should a suitable spouse be found, the male child will inform his father. The male spouse continues his visits to the lady (to seek, consent); the lady as it were, without a word, may have agreed, but still spouse face rather, she keeps looking on the floor or walk -scratching; possibly in the presence of a chaperone.^{xxxii}

^{xxvii} G. R. Quale. A History of Marriage Systems. Contributions in Family Studies, Number 13. New York: Greenwood. 1988 see also yorupedia.com

^{xxviii} A. Atolagbe, Semiotics and language interlarding in Yoruba traditional wedding bilingual discourse, Journal of English and Literature Vol.3 No. 7, 2012 pp. 158-165,

^{xxix} A. Atolagbe, Semiotics and language interlarding in Yoruba traditional wedding bilingual discourse, Journal of English and Literature Vol.3 No. 7, 2012 p. 159 see also yorupedia.com

^{xxx} Ibid p. 160

^{xxxi} Ibid

^{xxxii} C. O. Odejebi, Influence of Socio-Economic Change on Marriage Norms in the Yoruba Society, in Southwest Nigeria, Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy Vol 2 No 3, 2013

The next marriage step is "Ìsíùn" meaning "I accepted your proposal "after many visit to the prospective bride home, followed by exchange personal of gifts. At this time, all family reputation is already done and known. The lady feels it is time to consent, and move the relationship further after seeking parental advice and blessing on the matter.^{xxxiii}

When the lady agrees, marriage journey moves to the fourth and most important level "Ìtoro"^{xxxiv} that is soliciting for the prospective wife from father's house. This stage in marriage step is undertaken by the most senior males in the two houses, if the requests are granted, then the groom's family moves to the next crucial stage of marriage called Betrothals (Ìdána), second to the leg in Yoruba marriage.

Idana is the first public request of a female child, for hands in marriage from her father's house. At this occasion, items of both spiritual and social values are presented to the bride's family. These items are:

Honey (oyin)-a bottle of wild honey, the symbolic value of this item is that, couple's life will be as sweet as honey and be blessed with promising children. Alligator pepper (atare)-it comes in a pod with multiple seed; it symbolizes blessing, healthy and prosperous children for the couple.

Ground-nut cake (Àádàn)-it is a local cake made from ground nut, it signifies sweetness, blessing and prosperous future for the couple and their children.

Local wine (otí-sekete) - this represents water, which is life, treasured for its multiple uses. Since no one ever dislikes, hates, and speaks evil of water, so the couple will live a peaceful life, free from hate and dislike.^{xxxv}

Kola-nut (obí-àbàtà) with four halves, 42 or 100 pieces; in some cases it can more)-Kola-nut has several social and spiritual values in Yoruba land, when it comes to marriage; it symbolizes fertility and protection from evil. The Kola-nut brought on this day will be used to pray for the fruit of belly.

Bitter -nut (orógbó, 42 pieces; in some cases it can be more) represent old age, prosperity and trouble -free world .This means the couple will live a long life in good health and see generation of their children.

Palm oil (Epo-pupa) -it has several uses, one of which is the antidotal value. The palm oil suggests that no evil will befall or overcome the couple.

Salt (Iyò) - is used as a preservative and as a sweetener, symbolically; salt I in the life of the couple will represent joy and trouble -free life.

Yam (between 30 and 100 tubers) - this will depend on the status, wealth of the groom's family.

^{xxxiii} T. J. Akinbolaji, Marriage culture in Yorubaland, Nigeria, Africa <http://www.helium.com/items/1320012how-the-yorubas-valuedmarriage-in-thier-society>, 2009 see also D. Ogundoro. Marriage culture in Yorubaland, Nigeria, Africa. Helium inc. 2007

^{xxxiv} Ibid

^{xxxv} O. Akinloye. Yoruba People, Language, and Culture. Yoruba Language Program Students. University of Georgia, 1999

Prayers re said by families and other well-wishers. The ceremony legitimizes the couple's relationship, at this point; none of the party without a well-founded reason can back out of the relationship.^{xxxvi}

C. Hairdo

Head occupies a pre-eminent place compare with other part of the body; so too, the hair that covers the head. The culture and tradition of hair-do is rooted in both spiritual and biological role of individual head. The head is treasured and respected, because, it is the center of the body activity; through hairdo and care, *orí* (head) is highly esteemed.^{xxxvii}

In times past, even at present hairdo or styles perform several roles among Èkìtì people; these functions or roles include: medium of communication, mark of initiation, state of mind, religious beliefs marital and social status of woman in the society. For instance, a hair style from the forehead which end at the back of the neck shows the carrier is married; beside, married woman carry hair style from both sides of the head, and finish up at the middle of the head in such a network shape that connect the for head and back together. On the other hand, maiden style runs from the right side of the head to the ear. The smaller, and the more hair strands a young lady carries, the more beautiful such a lady will look. Maiden usually carry hair style of 8 to 14 strands, in braided or wrapped form.

Braiding and binding: (the use of thread to make strands) are the two common way to beautify hair by woman in the past. However, braiding (*irun biba*; knotting hair) comes in different styles these include: *sùkú* @a braiding hairstyle either short or long knots, it runs from forehead to back or crown of the head.^{xxxviii} *Kòlèsè*: as the name imply (without leg), it is a braiding style each knot runs from the front and terminates at the back of the head, close to the neck.^{xxxix} *Ìpàkó-elédè*: this braiding style starts from the back of the head, but ends at the front. *Panumó* - (keep quiet) - hair style, with two different starting points, the back and front. The knot meets at the center with a little opening.^{xl} *Òjòunpetí* (rain soaked ear)-braiding starts from one side of the head, end close to the ear.

^{xxxvi} The articles of prayer such as: kolanut, alligator pepper, bitter kola, honey etc, were used by the elderly person in the family to pray for the bride and the groom but in this contemporary world, the *Alaga Ijoko* performs the function of using these articles to pray for the bride and the groom. Those who are supposed to perform the function have become audience at the ceremony. By the evening period, the lady's mother will call her daughter and advice her on how to behave and live her life in her husband's house. Thereafter the eldest person in the family calls her to pray for her before giving her a departing gift. After this admonition and prayers, her family members and her friends will see her off with singing and dancing to her new home. See also C. O. Odejobi, *Influence of Socio-Economic Change on Marriage Norms in the Yoruba Society*, in *Southwest Nigeria, Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy Vol 2 No 3, 2013

^{xxxvii} T. Abioye, *A Socio-Cultural Analysis of Yoruba Discourse Patterns in selected Child Welfare Clinics in Southwestern Nigeria*. *Cross-cultural Communication* Vol. 7, No. 4, 2011, pp. 71-78

^{xxxviii} J. F. Oloidi, *The Economic History of Èkìtì*, PhD Thesis, University of Nsukka, 2011

^{xxxix} *Ibid*

^{xl} J. F. Oloidi, *The Economic History of Èkìtì*, PhD Thesis, University of Nsukka, 2011 p. 67

Arts and Craft: Èkìtì language is exceedingly unique and rich; it is laced with witty speeches, strong rhetoric which has qualities of (logo persuasion) pathos, experience and ethos. Yoruba art (a general term for: skill, artifact, craft, art, mastery language) which include, but not limited to: drama, dance, song, artifact, tragedy, trade-comedy. Collectively, they have become preserving agent as well as vehicle for transmission of Yoruba culture for centuries.^{xli}

Poetry is a metric or literary writing that convey a specific or multi message to its listening audience. Poetry may be written independently as a discrete poem, or synergize with other artistic work such as drama, hymns, lyrics, Yoruba poetry includes: Ewì, oríkì, Ìjálá, ekún Ìyàwó, or Ekúnn - rárá.^{xlii}

Oríkì (eulogy) - a praise, vocative statement for a person, a family, a group, or even an entire community. It is an organized poetic word in verse and mostly "nominalized" to expound individual /family attributes, qualities, successes, accomplishment combined with commonly shared community attributes.^{xliii} There is individual\family oríkì, group /community oríkì. Individual oríkì is a poetic assemblage of qualities, attributes and successes of prominent individual dead or alive; family or individual oríkì is perpetuated through names and continued narration of such oríkì. Every child at birth is given names with link to the family oríkì generally traceable to the paternal lineage.^{xliiv} Personal/family oríkì is learned by every family member by heart, while local drummer and professional praise singer also learn some oríkìs which are recited in honor of their owners at public functions.^{xliv}

Ìjálá -is hunter's chant which is directed at animal in the wild, whenever hunters are out for game. ìjálá focuses on animal attributes, only seasoned hunters recites ìjálá, to praise (animals) or to express happiness or disappointed when in the wild. Ìjálá poems are many and varied, we have ìjálá for different occasion, which may show or reflect the way of life of the community to whom belongs the heritage of ìjálá @chanting tradition. While ìjálá @chanter or cantor is cognizant of the special occasion of which his poem will focus, he is also at liberty to add, or to compose a new poem in his honour, or for individual who are alive and those dead.^{xlvi}

Ekún Ìyàwó,- is a bridal chant on the wedding night for the bride to-be, friend of the bride and older woman in the family pedigree, bride's good qualities, what the new life will be, and blessing that awaits the bride in her new home. The chant runs through the night, before the marriage.^{xlvii}

^{xli} N. A. Fadipe. *The Sociology of the Yoruba*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Ibadan University Press, 1970

^{xlii} S. A Akintoye, *Revolution and Power Politics in Yoruba-land 1840-1893*, London: Longman, 1971

^{xliiii} K. Barber. *I Could Speak until Tomorrow: Oríkì, Women and the Past in a YorùbáTown*. University Press, Edinburgh, 1991

^{xliiv} Interview with Chief S.O Osadola, 60, a traditional chief of Arámokọ Èkìtì, 3rd April 2018 see also O. Akinloye. *Yoruba People, Language, and Culture*. Yoruba Language Program Students. University of Georgia. 1999

^{xliv} S. A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 21

^{xlvi} S. A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 54

^{xlvii} ^{xlvii} S. O. Johnson. *The History of the Yorubas*, London: Lowe and Brydone Printers Limited, 1921. P. 22, see also S. A. Oguntuyi, *History of Èkìtì: From the Beginning to 1939*, Ibadan: Bisi Books, 1979 p. 21,

Iwì Egúngún- According to "Karin Berber in African folklore-encyclopedia © *Iwì Egúngún* is usually long passages addressing the legendary founder of ancestral masquerade cult. *Iwì* expound the qualities of past ancestors and their achievement.^{xlvi}

C. Entertainment

Prior to the introduction of western games into Lagos province by the British authority in mid nineteenth century, Yorubas had created, and occupied with a few engaging games both indoor and outdoor which are physically demanding, and designed for the entertainment of the general public. Games like wrestling (Eke, ijakadi, or Gidigbo),^{xlix} horse riding, swimming, and racing were normal. Wrestling is a two man battle, which usually takes place in special occasions and general market. The contenders are typically men; with the aim of knowing the strongest among them. The optional reason is, to search for youth leader to head their age set system. In most Èkìtì towns and villages, suitors were to take part in such physical challenges like wrestling or chasing to determine the most suitable of them all before young girls were given out in marriage.¹

3. Conclusion

This paper on the socio-cultural structure and development in pre-colonial Arámokò has been able to ascertain that just like every other communities in Èkìtì, Arámokò people are also rich in social and cultural antiquities. The strong and firm political structure headed by the Alára and his council members have impacted the community's intra-personal relationship and encouraged a peaceful co-existence. It shows that the various social and cultural institutions had been in existence prior the coming of the white man and will still be in existence notwithstanding the slight modification introduced by western education.

^{xlvi} T. Dzeka, O. S. Osadola, Social-Cultural and Institutional Diffusion in Western Nigeria: An Assessment of Benin Influence on Èkìtì, Makurdi Journal of Arts and Culture (MAJAC), Vol.13, 2015, p. 221

^{xlix} D. Ogundoro. Marriage culture in Yorubaland, Nigeria, Africa. Helium inc. 2007 see also T. Dzeka, O. S. Osadola, Social-Cultural and Institutional Diffusion in Western Nigeria: An Assessment of Benin Influence on Èkìtì, Makurdi Journal of Arts and Culture (MAJAC), Vol.13, 2015, p. 221

¹ G. R. Quale. A History of Marriage Systems. Contributions in Family Studies, Number 13. New York: Greenwood. 1988

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